

Thermal Decomposition and Structural Studies of Mixed-ligand Nickel(II) Complexes of *o*-Vanillin Anils and *N*-Heterocyclic Bases

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Manuscript received 8 November 1994, revised 31 October 1995, accepted 31 January 1996

A series of mixed-ligand Ni^{II} chelates formulated as [Ni(L/L'/L'')B] are formed in 1 : 1 : 1 stoichiometry where dianion is L = *o*-vanillinsemicarbazone (oVSC), L' = *o*-vanillinthiosemicarbazone (oVTSC) and L'' = *o*-vanillin-4-phenylthiosemicarbazone (oVPTSC); B = 2,2'-bipyridine, 1,10-phenanthroline or pyridine.

Mixed-ligand complexes wherein metal ions are bound to two different biochemically important ligands have aroused interest as models for the metalloenzymes. In these systems, both the chelating molecules may be simultaneously bound to the metal ion forming a mixed-ligand complex^{1,2}. The non-statistical factors affecting the stability of the ternary complex are mainly the hard and soft character of the ligands, electrostatic and steric effect and intramolecular interligand interactions.

Earlier we reported the mixed-ligand copper(II) complexes with Schiff base ligands derived from *o*-vanillin and heterocyclic bases³. Herein the synthesis, characterisation and thermal characteristics of mixed-ligand nickel(II) complexes with three Schiff base ligands are described.

Results and Discussion

The compositions of the complexes are in conformity with the general formula [Ni(L)B], where H₂L = oVSC, H₂L' = oVTSC and H₂L'' = oVPTSC; B = bipy, phen or py. In cases of oVSC(L) and oVTSC(L') the ternary complexes formed contain one molecule of coordinated water as evidenced by spectral (ir) and thermogravimetric data⁴ thus pertaining to the general formula [Ni(L/L')B.H₂O]. Other physical characterisation and low values of molar conductance, indicating non-electrolytic nature of the ternary complexes, are given in Table 1.

The complexes are insoluble in common organic solvents and soluble in polar solvents like dimethylformamide, dimethylsulphoxide and dioxan.

Infrared spectra : Formation of the Schiff base ligand is confirmed by the presence of band specific for ν_{C=N} and subsequent disappearance of bands due to the aldehydic and amine groups^{5,6}. Complexes show no bands due to phenolic OH and NH protons of the ligands. The C=O/C=S stretching frequency of the free ligand disappears in the spectra of the complexes indicating that the ligands are present in the thiol form in the complexes. The above statement is further supported by the presence of ν_{C-O}/ν_{C-S} bands in the spectra of the complexes only⁷. Phenolic oxygen is a bonding site to the metal ion after deprotona-

tion as indicated by the shift in stretching frequency of phenolic C-O by 20 cm⁻¹ to the higher side⁸ and presence of Ni-O stretching bands in the low frequency region of the complex spectra (Table 2)⁹. Characteristic band confirming the coordination of bipy/phen/py molecule is observed in the ir spectra of all the ternary complexes which is accompanied by the negative shift of ν_{N=(ring)} thus indicating the participation of ring nitrogen of heterocyclic base with the metal ion^{9,10}. The foregoing facts suggest the bonding sites of the ligands to be azomethine nitrogen, thiol sulphur/enolic oxygen and phenolic oxygen atom of the ligand molecule and two ring nitrogen atoms of the heterocyclic base in case of bipy/phen and one nitrogen atom in case of py complexes. In addition to these, oVSC and oVTSC ternary complexes possess one molecule of coordinated water as evidenced by specific bands in their ir spectra due to ν_{OH}, δ_{H₂O} and γ_{H₂O}¹¹.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND NMR SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.*/ (Colour, M.p. °C)	λ _m cm ² mol ⁻¹	δ
[Ni(L)bipy.H ₂ O] (Green, 360)	5.02	—
[Ni(L')bipy.H ₂ O] (Brown, 250)	9.72	9.25' (6,6'H), 7.20 (5,5'H), 7.88' (4,4'H), 8.65 (3,3'H),
[Ni(L'')bipy] (Brown, 230)	10.03	9.25'' (6,6'H), 6.90, (5,5'H), 7.75' (4,4'H), 9.00 (3,3'H),
[Ni(L)phen.H ₂ O] (Brown, 360)	8.58	—
[Ni(L')phen.H ₂ O] (Brown, 230)	4.50	—
[Ni(L'')phen] (Brown, 230)	10.03	9.20' (2,9H), 8.30 (4,7H), 7.54' (5,6H), 7.20 (3,8H),
[Ni(L)py.H ₂ O] (Green, > 360)	3.70	—
[Ni(L')py.H ₂ O] (Brown, > 360)	13.20	7.90' (2,6H), 7.52 (3,5H), 6.48 (4,H)
[Ni(L'')py.H ₂ O] (Brown, 200)	4.62	8.00' (2,6H), 7.52, (3,5H), 6.50 (4,H)

*H₂L = oVSC, H₂L' = oVTSC, H₂L'' = oVPTSC.

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TABLE 2—IR SPECTRAL DATA (ν_{\max} , cm^{-1}) OF MIXED-LIGAND COMPLEXES

Compd.	(C=N)	C=O/ C=S	C-O/ phenolic	N-N	C-O/ C-S	M-O/ M-S	M-N	Bands due to heterocyclic bases
H ₂ L	1 570	1 660	1 270	922	—	—	—	—
[Ni(L)bipy.H ₂ O]	1 630	—	1 268	950	1 390	380	412	520, 728, 1 012, 1 428
[Ni(L)phen.H ₂ O]	1 620	—	1 290	950	1 330	360	400	512, 730, 938, 1 445
[Ni(L)py.H ₂ O]	1 580	—	1 292	940	1 382	330	395	450, 625, 1 020, 1 225, 1 602
H ₂ L'	1 575	1 462	1 240	928	—	—	—	—
[Ni(L')bipy.H ₂ O]	1 592	—	1 300	960	840	370	410	440, 735, 1 012, 1 445
[Ni(L')phen.H ₂ O]	1 590	—	1 320	960	840	370	430	445, 730, 840, 1 450
[Ni(L')py.H ₂ O]	1 590	—	1 305	975	852	360	420	490, 665, 1 080, 1 435
H ₂ L''	1 525	1 460	1 268	925	—	—	—	—
[Ni(L'')bipy]	1 600	—	1 310	970	850	360	445	412, 725, 1 018, 1 440
[Ni(L'')phen]	1 590	—	1 305	970	835	360	430	420, 630, 832, 1 440
[Ni(L'')py]	1 600	—	1 312	972	860	380	475	420, 680, 1 020, 1 440

Magnetic data and diffuse reflectance spectra :

Octahedral complexes : Usually three *d-d* bands are expected for nickel(II) octahedral complexes in order of increasing energy :

However, ν_1 and ν_2 bands are obscured by the appearance of broad and diffuse reflectance band, suggesting a superimposition of more than one component into a single one¹². The magnetic moment values of Ni^{II} octahedral complexes are found to be 3.3, 3.5 B.M. for oVSC complexes with bipy and phen molecule respectively. The corresponding values are 3.20 and 2.73 B.M. for oVTSC ternary complexes which almost lie in the range of octahedral complexes.

Five-coordinated complexes : In case of oVPTSC mixed-ligand Ni^{II} complexes with bipy/phen, a band is observed at 430–440 and 340–330 nm respectively. A $\pi-\pi^*$ transition band of coordinated heterocyclic base is present at 310 nm in both cases. Magnetic susceptibility data show that the bipy complex is diamagnetic possessing an orbitally non-degenerate ground state and square-pyramidal geometry, whereas the similar complex with phen analogue showing a magnetic moment of 3.50 B.M. accounts for a large orbital contribution possessing an orbitally degenerate ground state and a trigonal bipyramidal geometry. In case of mixed-ligand complexes with py and oVSC/oVTSC, the magnetic moment values are found to be 2.80 and 3.46 B.M. respectively, corresponding to a low-spin square-pyramidal geometry. Two bands are observed at 430, 380 and 420, 370 nm due to the transitions. ${}^3A_{1g} \leftarrow {}^3E_{1g}$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \leftarrow {}^3E_{1g}$ respectively; spectral band due to the coordinated pyridine molecule is observed due to the $\pi \leftarrow \pi^*$ transition at ~320 nm in all the pyridine mixed-ligand complexes.

Tetrahedral complex : The mixed-ligand Ni^{II} complex with oVPTSC and py is four-coordinated having distorted tetrahedral geometry as manifested by its magnetic moment of 3.34 B.M. ${}^3T_{1G} \leftarrow {}^3A_{2g}$ transition is indicated by a band at 400 nm. Another band at 375 nm is assigned to the transition to the *3p* manifold.

TABLE 3—TG DATA OF TERNARY COMPLEXES*

Compd.	% Weight-loss	
	Found	Calcd.
[Ni(L)bipy.H ₂ O]	5.81	5.60
[Ni(L)phen.H ₂ O]	4.82	4.58
[Ni(L)py.H ₂ O]	4.97	5.00
[Ni(L')bipy.H ₂ O]	4.96	4.82
[Ni(L')phen.H ₂ O]	4.62	4.50
[Ni(L')py.H ₂ O]	4.80	4.75

*Other complexes do not contain water molecule.

Thermogravimetric analysis and nmr spectra : A perusal of the pyrolytic curves gives detail information regarding the mode of decomposition and temperature range for the loss of different molecules at various stages. Ternary complexes (Fig. 1) seem to be less stable than their binary analogues with formation of thermally stable intermediates in between the sharp decomposition curve¹³. The presence of one molecule of water of coordination has been confirmed in case of ternary complexes with oVSC by the weight-loss corresponding to 1 water molecule in the temperature range 100–140^o (Table 3). The thermal degradation pattern of these ternary complexes may be represented as

On comparing the thermogravimetric data of all the complexes, the order of stability of various complexes is estimated taking the decomposition temperature as a measure of the thermal stability : [Ni(L)bipy.H₂O] < [Ni(L)phen.H₂O] < [Ni(L)py.H₂O], [Ni(L')bipy.H₂O] < [Ni(L')phen.H₂O] < [Ni(L')py.H₂O], [Ni(L'')py] < [Ni(L'')bipy] < [Ni(L'')phen]. The lowest stability of oVPTSC complexes may be attributed to the electron-withdrawing substituent, the phenyl group on the ligand molecules which invokes

steric hindrance in the complex.

Prominent bands are observed in the proton nmr spectra of the complexes due to the ring protons of coordinated heterocyclic molecules, viz. bipy, phen or py. The ring protons of bipy give rise to three multiplets at 9.25, 7.88 and 7.20 ppm^{15,16} in Ni^{II}-oVTSC ternary complex. Bands due to proton signals in complexes containing phen¹⁷ and bipy, py^{18,19} molecules are included in Table 1.

Fig 1. TG curves of mixed ligand Ni-oVTSC complexes.

Conclusion : The complexation of the ternary complexes occurs through deprotonated enolic form of the Schiff base oVSC, oVTSC or oVPTSC, its azomethine nitrogen and deprotonated *ortho*-hydroxy group in addition to one molecule of heterocyclic base and one molecule of coordinated water to yield 4-, 5- and 6-coordinated complexes.

Experimental

o-Vanillin, semicarbazide hydrochloride, thiosemicarbazide (Sisco), Ni(OOCCH₃)₂·4H₂O, 2,2'-bipyridine, 1,10-phenanthroline and pyridine, diethyl ether, dimethylformamide (E. Merck) and 4-phenylthiosemicarbazide (Aldrich) were used.

The ligands : Schiff base ligand was prepared by refluxing equimolar concentrations of *o*-vanillin (0.05 mol, 7.65 g) with semicarbazide (0.05 mol, 5.52 g), thiosemicarbazide (0.05 mol, 4.56 g) or 4-phenylthiosemicarbazide (0.05 mol, 8.36 g) for 4 h to yield the corresponding Schiff bases *o*-vanillinsemicarbazone (oVSC; 8.29 g, 95%), *o*-vanillinthiosemicarbazone (oVTSC; 9.20 g, 85.50%) and *o*-vanillin-4-phenylthiosemicarbazone (oVPTSC; 8.62 g, 90.25%). The products were washed with ethanol and ether and subsequently dried in vacuum over fused CaCl₂. The purity was checked by tlc.

Mixed-ligand Ni^{II} complexes : A 0.005 M solution of Schiff base ligand (1.05 g oVSC, 1.13 g oVTSC and 1.50 g oVPTSC) was prepared in DMF and stirred with 0.005 M ethanolic solution of the base (0.78 g bipy, 0.99 g phen and 0.40 ml pyridine) for 2 h. To it an aqueous nickel acetate solution (0.005 M; 1.24 g) was added and the mixture was refluxed for 4 h on a heating mantle. Bright coloured ternary complexes that separated on cooling at 0° for 24 h

were washed with ethanol and ether and dried in vacuum over CaCl₂. The complexes were crystallised from DMF : **2** (Found : C, 44.03; H, 4.01; N, 14.50; Ni, 13.11. C₁₉H₁₉N₅O₄Ni calcd. for : C, 51.85; H, 4.32; N, 15.92; Ni, 13.35%); **3** (Found : C, 43.83; H, 4.18; N, 16.45; Ni, 13.11. C₂₁H₁₉N₅O₄Ni calcd. for : C, 54.34; H, 4.10; N, 15.09; Ni, 12.65%); **4** (Found : C, 43.45; H, 4.21; N, 16.55; Ni, 15.73. C₁₄H₁₆N₄O₄Ni calcd. for : C, 46.32; H, 4.41; N, 15.44; Ni, 16.18%); **6** (Found : C, 44.07; H, 3.83; N, 13.79; Ni, 13.50. C₁₉H₁₉N₅O₃SNi calcd. for : C, 50.03; H, 4.17; N, 15.36; Ni, 12.88%); **7** (Found : C, 44.80; H, 3.69; N, 13.04; Ni, 14.76. C₂₁H₁₉N₅OSNi calcd. for : C, 52.53; H, 3.96; N, 14.60; Ni, 12.24%); **8** (Found : C, 37.66; H, 3.05; N, 13.70; Ni, 14.98. C₁₄H₁₆N₄O₃SNi calcd. for : C, 44.36; H, 4.22; N, 14.78; Ni, 15.50%); **10** (Found : C, 54.93; H, 4.27; N, 12.63; Ni, 10.40. C₂₅H₂₁N₅O₂SNi calcd. for : C, 58.40; H, 4.08; N, 13.63; Ni, 11.43%); **11** (Found : C, 55.39; H, 3.97; N, 12.03; Ni, 12.00. C₂₇H₂₁N₅O₂SNi calcd. for : C, 60.26; H, 3.90; N, 13.02; Ni, 10.91%); **12** (Found : C, 54.38; H, 4.22; N, 12.54; Ni, 11.96. C₂₀H₁₈N₄O₂SNi calcd. for : C, 54.96; H, 4.12; N, 12.82; Ni, 13.44%). The lower value of carbon may be due to the fair solubility⁴ of the ternary complexes in the solvent employed.

Nickel was estimated gravimetrically²⁰. C, H and N were determined micro-analytically using a Carlo-Erba 1106 analyser. Ir spectra (CsI) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 1430 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra (DMF) on a Perkin-Elmer SP-800 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra on a WH-270 spectrometer. Magnetic susceptibility was measured by the Gouy's method using Hg[Co(SCN)₄] as calibrant at room temperature. Conductivity of the complexes was measured (10⁻³ M in DMF) at room temperature on a Toshniwal instrument.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. C. L. Khetrapal, Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore, for providing nmr facilities to R.S.I.C., Central Drug Research Institute for C, H, N analysis, to R.S.I.C., Nagpur for thermogravimetric analysis and to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for financial support to one of them (S.H.).

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